

Silicon Carbide(SiC) Thin Film Deposited On Silicon- An Interesting NIR Emission

Kusumita Kundu¹, Ashok Ranjan², N. Eshwara. Prasad ² and Rajat Banerjee¹

1. CSIR- Central Glass and Ceramic Research Institute, Kolkata-700032, India

2. Defence Materials & Stores Research & Development Establishment, Kanpur-208013, India

Email id of corresponding Author: rajatbanerjee@hotmail.com Mobile Number: 9433574055

Abstract:

Research on crystalline silicon carbide (SiC) thin film exhibits strong visible and NIR emission due to its wide band gap¹. Polymer derived SiC thin film has been of great interest due to its high thermal stability and good mechanical properties. This paper deals with deposition of SiC thin film on Silicon (Si) wafer using boron doped Liquid Polycarbosilane (PCS) by Modified Chemical Vapour Deposition (MOCVD).

The film was characterised by GA-XRD and X- ray photoelectron spectroscopy. The GA-XRD plot indicates formation of β -3C SiC Nano crystals. The binding energy diagrams obtained from XPS ascertain the presence of boron ² and amorphous carbon into the SiC matrix.

Finally, The Photoluminescence spectra (PL) shows a unique NIR emission from 750 nm to 900 nm on excitation of 532 nm laser. This indicates that the boron doped SiC thin film on Si can be a promising material for the fabrication of different optoelectronic devices.

Keywords: Silicon Carbide; Nano crystal; Thin Film

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